

Impact of Big Data Analytics on Social Media

Jignesh Sunil Naik

Department of MCA, YMT College of Management, Kharghar, Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra, India

ABSTRACT

Social Media has wider scope in today’s World. There are over 900 social media sites available in the market. so that the massive information from that sites and problem with that info is storage. It is a popular way for people to expressing their thoughts and feelings and another important aspect in this study is Sentimental Analysis which is a study that include to analyze people’s opinion and importance is to decide the achievement of social network The main aim of this study is to find different technique for analyzing social media information.

KEYWORDS: Big data Analytics, Predictive analysis, Hadoop, text mining, Natural language processing

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INTRODUCTION

Big data become an important topic in many areas where dataset are so large. In computer science, it known as dataset are too big to handled. it is obvious that large dataset can be handled in different way than the smaller one. The problem encountered while dealing with data are capture, analytic and visualization. The e.g. such as astronomy, biological, high energy physics data is in peta and extabytes in which storage is the biggest challenge but there are new domain to solve big data problem. big data characteristics are Volume, Velocity, Variety and variant for data Storage and management.

Nowadays social media is most popular for promoting the product. In social media people will express their opinion which can be positive, negative, neutral. so to judge that opinion the procedure is used called as opinion mining[7] which uses text mining and natural language processing procedure to understand emotions by the computer. for e.g. Facebook is an social media network for connecting to users. in past few days Facebook platform is exponentially grown. Facebook marketing good in B2C (business to consumer) businesses.

[1] **Figure1: Social Media Operations**

- Encapsess wide variety of content formats.
 - text, audia, video, photographs, pdf, ppt etc.
- Support one or more plateforms
 - social sharing, e-mail, feed etc.
- Different levels of engagements
 - share, comment, like, alter etc.
- Scalable communication for masses
 - one-one, one-many, many - many
- Device Independent
 - Indifferent for mobile, palmtop, pc etc.
- Support Real time as well as offline mode
 - live contents sharing with option for offline

Figure 2: Characteristics of Social Media [2]

Literature review:-

[3] “Big data Analytics on social media data“, author prashant sahatiya discussed the techniques For analyze

social media data and tools which helpful in developing business plan[Feb-2018].

[4] “The value of big data in digital media research”, author Merja and Michael describe although there are pitfalls in the social media, the researcher should define the approaches to find out the results[2013].

[5] “Big data and social media to improve quality of higher education”, author Dr. Savita Kumari talks about changes in the education field because of social media [2016].

[6] “social media analytics”, author Stefan, Milad, Bjorn and Christoph focused on challenges and difficulties face by the researcher during collection, diagnosis of data and derive [2017].

[7] “To study social media and sentimental analysis using Facebook as a platform”, author Yogen desai mentioned challenge face during textual based data and also tells that use of digital data in the research of social science[Feb-2017].

Objective of the study:

- inquiry and feedback of people which help to determine control of brand.
- To study the promotion activities while developing the brand.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:-

➤ **Social media data analysis**

In this analysis the data will collected from massive source or unstructured sources for e.g. Likes, comments and views will be analyzed. It also plays very important role in the business. Facebook have billions of users, so the analyzing data that is in different form will be difficult.

Analysis of social media data help to improve business and make profit to the business. The technologies like Hadoop and Cloud Analytics is important for storing massive information and improve the quality of business.

➤ **Key Technologies for analytics of social media data:** There are lots of technologies that will assist your data. the list of technology which is as follows :

- Data Mining:- It allows to generate patterns that will used to analyze any queries.
- Data management: - It is crucial to maintain quality of information. So there will be a program which helps to maintain the information of particular page.
- Predictive analysis:-predictive analysis is about predicting what will be happen in future that help organization to make powerful brand.
- Text mining:- This process include analyze text based information which can be books, comment field. In this e-mail, blogs, survey and twitter feed uses machine learning technology to analyze the knowledge.
- In-memory analytics:- It allows you to analyze information from system memory. it will allow to access to information instantly.

➤ **Tools used for big data analytics:-**

- Agora Pulse: This tool is used to identify user needs and best content.

- Brand Watch: It is all about data usage for excellent market functions.
- Brand Mentions: It is about for measuring social media marketing impact.
- Reputology: It involves monitoring and analyzing your reviews online so that it is easy to handle bad reviews.
- Net Base: It provide social analytics for your brand.

➤ **Data Analysis:**

The data collected from various respondents through questionnaires’ which contain data of Users that are active on the Facebook. e.g. there are categories of 200 respondents.

Table No.1- Average Ratio of Male and Female users according to their age[7]

Age	Male	Female
15-30	40	30
30-50	22	40
50-70	15	6
70-100	7	3

Table No.2- Average time users spend on Facebook [7]

Activeness	Avg
Daily	70
Once in week	4
Twice in week	10
Once in month	3

Table No.3- User opinion on Facebook advertisement [7]

	Yes	No	Not enough	Can't say
Does Facebook Provide opportunities to promote brand	60	10	5	17

Questionnaires include the personal information and perception towards social media Promotions and also include usage pattern of social media[7].

Fig 1.1 [7]

Fig 1.2 [7]

Conclusion:-

This paper describe different tools and techniques for interpreting social media data With the help of the sampling data of 200 respondents that are live on the Facebook. and it is also useful improve performance of the business. Furthermore, social media data are also improve quality of education and also predictive analysis for the future.

Challenges:-

Social media data are very critical data. the data is increasing day by day So the biggest challenge is to secure that data and maintain privacy of the people. because nowadays hackers are monitor your data i.e. comments, likes and views that will convert data in such way that you are looking like

criminal. Sometimes the peoples will create fake profiles so it is difficult to verify the identity of the people.

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